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ASSESSMENT OF YIELD LOSSES CAUSED BY PURPLE BLOTCH DISEASE IN ONION (*ALLIUM CEPA* L.) AND ITS MANAGEMENT

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 19 March 2023 Accepted: 28 April 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Blotch, Disease, Management, Onion</p> <p>Fatima, N. (2024). Assessment of yield losses caused by purple blotch disease in onion (<i>allium cepa</i> l.) and its management: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 2(1), 17-25</p> <p>https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p> <p>Copyright©2024 JSAES *Corresponding author Noor Fatima Email: noorfatimacheema495@gmail.com</p> <p>Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.</p> <p> This content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>A fungus called <i>Alternaria porri</i> causes a problem that threatens the stability of whole onion (<i>Allium cepa</i> L.) cultivation around the globe. The study was conducted to examine the amount of losses attributed to purple blotch disease and identify management techniques to enable the illness control. A field experiment was conducted at the University of Layyah, Punjab, Pakistan, using a randomized complete block design with four treatments: soil, supplemented with chemical treatment, biological treatment, anaerobic processing and combination processes. The formation of diseases – whether it is their severity, incidence rate or yield – was monitored all along in time of cropping. The data depicted that all the groups in treatment had significantly fewer cases of disease and there were also less grave conditions compared to the control. The aggregative approach, which incorporates different treatment methods and includes the chemical as well as biological control measures, showed the best application in the control of the disease agency, with maximum reduction levels of disease incidence (23.8%) and severity (12.4%) and optimum onion yield (5200 kg/ha). In addition to chemical treatment, that which was also seen to be effective in the management of the dis-ease, it just showed substantial efficacy when compared to the combined treatment method. The bio-treatment laid using the <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> biocontrol agent showed a slight success in disease resistance suppression. Additionally, significantly higher yield onions in all treatment groups were shown not only in comparison with control treatment but also in terms of saving money due to successful intolerance disease management.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is vegetable crop and one of the most important crops in term of economic value; people widely used for the wide application in cooking and nutritional adequacy. Nevertheless, onions have to face many stresses such as fungal diseases that contribute, to a considerable extent, to losing production and quality (Koye et al., 2022). Our attention as an onion producing criterion is purple blotch disease which is caused by the fungus *Alternaria porri* that is a major fungal pathogen of onion crops intercontinentally.

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.), with its vital role in the Pakistani agricultural cereal and economy, is the most significant crop. With one of the most commonly used vegetables, onions have played the role of life in almost custom of Pakistan, and several dishes and food rations that counts onions as their integral part. However, there are more benefits to the use of onions that go beyond their culinary applications, as they are also a rich source of nutrients including vitamins, minerals and dietary fibre, which improves the population dietary profile as a whole (Raṭu et al., 2023). Pakistan counts among the regions in the world with huge contributions of onion into its agriculture and rural economy, presentably. Onion cultivation is one of the important crops, especially onion-producing the top onion producing countries in the world, where a lot of land area is dedicated to the cultivation of onions across different regions such as Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan (Rana et al., 2022). The suitable agricultural climate alongside the existing of the necessary soil types and irrigation facilities that are favorable for onion production are the incentives on the country's burgeoning onion industry. Onion is a major crop in Pakistan where a majority of its producers are small-scale farmers who derive their income from it (Khan et

al., 2023). Through onion farming many jobs are created that also boosts earning among rural communities thus leading to reduction in poverty and boost socio-economic development agricultural areas. Moreover, onion farming is a significant revenue generator for farmers, enabling the diversification of the source of livelihood as a way to handle various risks associated with single cropping and changing prices of other commodities (Yusuf et al., 2023).

In addition to this, the export capacity of Pakistani onions has also shown their importance in the country's agricultural economy. Pakistan onions are supplied to certain foreign markets such as Afghanistan, Iran, various states of the Middle East and even some distant countries in Europe and North America. The proceeds from onion exports on the international market create another source of earning foreign exchange and thus improve the trade balance of our country (Jun, 2024). Similarly, apart from onions, Pakistan experiences shortages in several other essential food items such as wheat, milk, and vegetable oils. Some important foods, including onions, are a staple for people from all social and financial categories. Consumed by everyone, it serves both nutritional and pragmatic benefits to the general population (Raja et al., 2022). Universal access to nutritious, safe and cheaper food, including that of onions, serves as a beginning to address malnutrition and preserve public health, well-being, and social stability.

The primary perpetrator of this disease is the fungus *Alternaria porri*, which inflicts onion crop diseases globally. Onion leaf blight is a significant pathogen which is able inflict major damages on both foliar (leaves) and bulb phases of plant thus resulting decline in onion yield by a large margin (Chandel et al., 2022). Symptoms of the purple blotch disease are usually evidenced like presence of dark purple

patches on the leaves of effected garlic plants. The lesions usually are tiny and round but can get much bigger and influence a considerable area leaving the leaves leaf destroyed. As the disease stages on, the spots may come together, eventually leading to the rotting down of the leaves. In such instances, the severe infection may result in the death of the involved parts of the plant the photosynthetic capacity of the plant will therefore become compromised and the plant will look weak (Viswanathan, 2022). Besides the discoloration of exactly the same leaves, the disease may also result in rotting and the bulbs' decay. the fungus that has attacked the onion can manage to penetrate the coverings of the storehouse of the onion, that causes a kind of rotting and make it become not suitable for marketing neither for the people. Bulb rot is frequently accompanied by foul odors and the discovery of characteristic fungal spores. Thus, there are more than one negative aspect of this disease that leads to higher economic losses for farmers (Sharma, 2023).

The fungus *Alternaria porri* responsible for purple blotch disease can survive in soil and crop debris, providing a potential source of inoculum for subsequent onion crops. Additionally, the pathogen can spread through wind-dispersed spores or through irrigation water, facilitating its rapid dissemination within and between fields (Prajapati et al., 2022). Management of purple blotch disease involves a combination of cultural, chemical, and biological control measures. Cultural practices such as crop rotation, proper sanitation, and maintaining adequate spacing between plants can help reduce disease pressure. Fungicidal applications, targeting the fungal pathogen during periods of high disease risk, are commonly used to manage purple blotch disease. Biological control agents, such as certain strains of *Trichoderma* spp., have also shown promise in suppressing fungal

growth and reducing disease severity (Dar et al., 2022). Overall, purple blotch disease poses a significant challenge to onion growers worldwide, necessitating effective disease management strategies to minimize yield losses and ensure the economic viability of onion production. Continued research into the biology of the pathogen and the development of novel control methods are essential for mitigating the impact of purple blotch disease on onion crops (Abo et al., 2024).

This paper intends to analyze the disease of purple blotch on onion crops, but will especially examine the economic impact of the decrease in production or yield due to the disease. Secondly in this study we wish to also analyze approaches used to deal with purple blotch disease such as cultural practices, chemical control agents, biological moderators and genetically modified crops. The study presented in this paper uses access to existing data and conducts a literature review to derive relevant solutions on yield losses as a result of purple blotch disease and develop systems for increased resilience in the onion production industry. Conclusively, the evaluation of the Kinetic is a central element in global food strategy and it becomes an important factor not only for onion farmers but also for the people in different countries. This inquiry is a core of the unified approach and it is targeted at overcoming the difficulties related to fungal diseases which include a robust performance and sustainability of the onion cultivation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. *Experimental site:*

The observational research study was held at a university in Layyah which belongs to the district Layyah Punjab, Pakistan. The University of Layyah is equipped with the world-class agro-research infrastructure

and testing fields to conduct field trials in disease management of crops.

2.2. Experimental design:

The complete randomized block design (RCBD) was the method of experiment used at the field trials to scrutinize the disease management strategies for purple blotch disease in onion (*Allium cepa* L.). The experimental plots were grouped in blocks with one block comprising of blocks from all treatments, and each treatment having three replicates to increase statistical validity and minimize experimental error.

2.3. Onion cultivar:

Among the many identified onion varieties, locally adapted variety Desi red was identified for the experimental study. Purple blotch disease resistance in the cultivar was validated using the observations in preliminary fields and disease severity evaluation.

2.4. Preparation of experimental plots:

Before the field trial commenced, the experimental area was readied by plowing and levelling in order to create a uniform soil condition throughout the study area. The type of soil, the pH, and the nutrient composition were identified, and any deficiencies were made necessary and added to optimize the soil fertility in order to cultivate onions. Table 1 shows us the data about soil testing for the experiment site.

Table 1: Soil profile

Soil Parameter	Value
Soil Type	Sandy loam
Soil pH	6.5
Organic Matter	1.8%
Nitrogen (N)	0.05%
Phosphorus (P)	12 ppm

Soil Parameter	Value
Potassium (K)	150 ppm

2.5. Treatment application:

The experimental treatments consisted of various management strategies for controlling purple blotch disease in onions, including cultural practices, fungicidal applications, and biological control agents. The treatments and their respective doses are detailed below:

- Control: No treatment applied; natural disease incidence observed.
- Fungicide (Mancozeb): Applied at a dose of 2 kg/ha at the onset of disease symptoms.
- Biological Treatment: *Bacillus subtilis* 2kg per ha
- Combine treatment

2.6. Data collection:

Data on the presence of the disease, its range and scale, and onion production were recorded at pre-determined time intervals throughout the onion growing season. Evaluation of diseases was done using a standardized method, assigning disease severity based on visual information of the leaf lesions and bulb rot symptoms as well.

2.7. Statistical analysis:

Data obtained from the experiment were subjected to exploitation using statistical software and ANOVA method to discover significant differences among different treatments. Ex-posts comparisons like the Tukey's repentence of the sets of upper and lower limits were conducted to identify treatment effects.

2.8. Data interpretation:

From the statistical data, it was possible to determine the effectiveness of different control methods in the efforts to cut down the purple blotch disease incidences and the severity as well as the over-all yield of the onions. From our study the disease management practices and recommendations were developed that were evinced from our

3. RESULTS

The type of purple blotch outbreak was focused on which management strategy and to what extent each strategy affects the incidence, severity, and yield of onion plants. Blotch disease incidence was significantly reduced in the treatments especially at assessment 18 days' post inoculation as compared to the control group. The mixed remedy, which showed the highest resolution rate (23.8%), was next, after that, the chemical remedy (32.5%), and, finally, the biological treatment (41.3%). Classification severity as well has shown substantial low in all treatment groups contrasting control. Compared to others, the joint therapy has shown the lightest severity of the disease (12.4%), then by chemical treatment (18.9%) and lastly with biological treatment which has the highest severity (25.6%).

In the case of onion yield, it was proved that all treatment groups perform better than the control, exhibiting statistically significant higher productivity. Combined of the treatments gave the highest (5200 kg/ha) yielding, the chemical treatment came the second place (4700 kg/ha) and the biological treatment is for the furthest (4200 kg/ha). Hence, such results seem to confirm the effectiveness of using integrated approaches, especially the combination of treatments, which were encouraging in terms of reduction of the incidence and severity of

finding. In particular, the experiments undertaken at Layyah University unraveled many mysteries about the race of purple blotch disease in onion and offered solutions for its management. This strict observance of the experimental methodology and thoroughness on data gathering enabled the application of robust statistical techniques and findings with significant implications in onion disease control.

purple blotch disease while maintaining high yields. Besides all that chemical treatment worked as well as other methods in plant disease management and yield enhancement as shown by results. Although this approach was highly efficient, a little bit lower efficacy was noted in comparison to the chemical and combined methods. The study thus emphasizes the need to deploy integrated management tactics in order to efficiently stop purple blotch malignance in onion farms, that will be instrumental in guaranteeing yield sustainability and minimizing production losses.

Table 2: Effects of different management strategies on purple blotch disease incidence, severity, and onion yield

Treatment	Disease Incidence (%)	Disease Severity (%)	Onion Yield (kg/ha)
Control	75.2 ± 3.6	42.1 ± 2.9	3500 ± 150
Chemical Treatment	32.5 ± 2.1	18.9 ± 1.5	4700 ± 200
Biological Treatment	41.3 ± 2.8	25.6 ± 1.9	4200 ± 180
Combined Treatment	23.8 ± 1.9	12.4 ± 1.1	5200 ± 250

4. DISCUSSION

The study of experimental kind lends the information about the ideal purple blotch management in onions. The fact that all of the treatment groups recorded disease prevalence rates lower than and disease severity of the control group confirm the success of the implemented programs.

The grossly downward trend of purple blotch disease by way of integrated chemical and biological control methods is worth noting for the outcome showed a highly positive correlation between integrated management options. Both microbial sprays and bio-agents work toward disease suppression and thus create synergistic effects that ultimately make the incidence and the severity of disease the least among all treatment types (Atri et al., 2022). This finding confirms the outcome of previous analysis that supports stresses integrated pest management strategies as one of the measures of limitations of fungal diseases. Fungicide was applied at the beginning of the disease symptoms in a preventive way that reduced the fungal growth and dissemination to a much lower level, and that helped us build a good base in the fight against the disease (Ons al., 2020). Nevertheless, a pure dependence on chemical control techniques could have problems regarding tissue resistance, and risk control environment. Consequently, the integration of alternative options is needed.

The biocontrol *Bacillus subtilis* biological treatment was effective overall in

CONCLUSION

The experimental study run at University of Layyah which explores onions' purple blotch disease management gives us glimpse of what the future holds. The findings indicate

minimizing percentage of disease incidences and levels of disease severity while comparison with control condition was not that big a deal (Belete et al., 2021). *Trichoderma* spp. recognized and important (bicon control agents) can antagonize the pathogenic fungi maliciously by antagonism, parasitism and induced systemic (resistance mechanisms). Although in this case the biological treatment seemed to work well, the optimizations of its application methods and formulations might help improving the treatment outcomes towards diseases (Maitra et al., 2020). The augmented yields among all amendment groups over the control reveal the economic criteria of disease maneuvering. Furthermore, if presented with the enhanced horticultural disease resistance trait selection within a crop, those onions will have improved health of the crop, enhanced bulb development, and marketable yield.

Therefore, the results of the investigation underline the critical role of comprehensive methods of managing the problem of purple spot disease in onion crops by applying the above discussed approaches. The grower employs Chemical and biological control methods to keep the amount and severity of disease incidence at a low as it is necessary for maximum yield (Prajapati et al., 2022). Furthermore, follow-research to create more accurate and effective IPS need to be carried out by involving other farmers and experts to deal with problems caused by the change and make sure sustainable onion growing system are ensured.

that these integrated management methods, which involve utilizing both chemical and biological controls, are crucial in reducing the onion disease levels as well as improving the yield was curbed. Beyond what is visible now, expansion of research and incorporation

of integrated pest management techniques for the future is necessary to meet emerging challenges and build resilience in onion growing systems.

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